

A COMPLEX SYSTEMIC ISSUE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NETWORK OF TRADE SERVICES.

Maxmatqulov G'olibjon Xolmuminovich

QarMII mustaqil izlanuvchisi

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Introduction. In order for the econometric modeling of the innovative development of trade services to have a strategic nature, its level of coverage is relevant in terms of relevance in the field, it is formed under systematic influence, the result of which is directly connected to the change of the most important industry indicators, and the interrelationship of issues that embody elements of priority. It is required to consist of a coherent, systematic complex.

Such a complex was formed in its own way. Its level, completeness, importance can be explained by the relevance of the issues that cause the need for modeling in the research of the field. Below are the complex systemic issues of the trade services network that require econometric research (Table 1.1).

In order to propose the development of a certain economic sector in terms of territory, it is first necessary to study the trend of its development in the region. In this case, the hardware is statistical analysis, and limiting it to this will not be enough to come to important conclusions. Derivative indicators (relative, absolute differences, etc.) that arise when the main trend indicators are statistically analyzed in two geographical areas are evaluated as a simple information indicator and do not allow to be evaluated as a factor. This creates the need for econometric analysis.

Innovative development of trade services is based on innovative development and economic potential of the region. An important element of the self-development nature of the network is reflected here. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to the issue of structural assessment of the weight of trade services in the dynamics of increasing the economic potential of the region. Here, it is important to determine the relationship between the relativity indicator of the dynamics of economic potential and the trend of change of the ratio lines obtained according to the macro-economic indicators of trade services as factors affecting it, and to assess the level of influence.

Also, a scientific prediction of future trends of indicators for evaluating the potential for innovative development of trade services is necessary (Table 1.1).

Table 1.1.

Complex systemic issues of development of trade services network

Economic problem-solving (in the narrow sense)	Systematized form	A mechanism for obtaining a solution (scientific reasoning)
Separation of the main and derivative signs that are important in the development trend of the industry in the region	Development of a system of important indicators for the development trend of the industry, assessment of mutual and complex effects	Conducting statistical and econometric analysis, developing adequate empirical models of assessment
Structural assessment of the importance of trade services in the dynamics of increasing the economic competence of the region	Forming a system of relativity indicators in the dynamics of increasing economic potential, determining the negative ratio of the system	Conducting econometric analysis, developing adequate dynamic econometric models for evaluating the interaction of relativity indicators
Assessment of the potential of innovative development of trade services for the population of the region	Forming a system of assessment factors for the potential for innovative development of trade services for the population, creating a form of communication, and determining the level of efficiency of the potential	Conducting econometric analysis, developing adequate econometric models for calculating forecast values of impact factors
Creating criteria for determining the trend of sustainable growth of trade services in the region	Developing a system of criteria that determines the asymptotic line of development that determines the level of conditional economic growth in the future of the development of trade services	Construction of balance equations according to sectoral indicators, determination of cross-industry trend lines, construction of a complex, time- and dimensional function-dependent econometric

		model expressing the condition for achieving stability of the trend - an expression of criteria for determining the asymptotic line
Organization of competitive innovative activities of trade enterprises	Determining the main factors of the organization of innovative activities of trade enterprises in a healthy competitive environment, calculating the efficiency index for innovative activities	Development of the efficiency index calculation algorithm for competitive innovative activities of trade enterprises
Forecasting the prospective main indicators of innovative development of trade services in the region	Determining prospective priorities for the innovative development of trade services	Development of adequate models of multi-scenario forecasting

Determining the trend of sustainable growth of trade services in the region requires the formation of a system of the most basic issues. Here, it is necessary to develop such criteria that, in the future, it will be necessary to determine the asymptotic line for the target economic growth indicators of the long-term sector and their parameters. Here, the asymptotic function results from econometric relationships.

In the organization of innovative activities of trade enterprises in the environment of healthy competition, there is a problem of determining the factors that ensure healthy competition between competitors. The only tool to solve this problem is econometric modeling of the competitive process.

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